

Tirzepatide in Obstructive Sleep Apnea: A Bibliometric Analysis

 Gülşah ETHEMOĞLU¹

¹Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Harran University, Sanliurfa, Türkiye

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Corresponding author: Gülşah Ethemoğlu
E-mail: gulsahethemoglu@gmail.com

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ORCID ID

GE: 0000-0002-6898-8911

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a highly prevalent sleep-related breathing disorder closely associated with obesity and cardiometabolic dysfunction. Recent advances in incretin-based therapies, particularly tirzepatide, have generated increasing interest in metabolically targeted approaches for OSA management.

Objective: This study aimed to comprehensively map and analyze global research trends on tirzepatide in OSA, with a focus on publication output, citation patterns, geographic and institutional contributions, collaboration networks, and thematic structures. **Methods:** A comprehensive bibliometric analysis was conducted using the Web of Science (WoS; Clarivate Analytics) database. The literature was searched from 2022, corresponding to the initial clinical introduction of tirzepatide, through September 18, 2025. Bibliometric indicators were evaluated using performance analysis, network analysis, and multiple correspondence analysis to assess research productivity, citation dynamics, international collaboration, and conceptual structures.

Results: A total of 39 publications with a total of 363 citations were identified, with a marked increase in publication output and citation activity after 2023. The United States and Australia were the leading contributors, and scientific production was concentrated among a limited number of authors and institutions. Keyword co-occurrence analysis revealed three principal thematic clusters: pharmacological, cardiometabolic, and respiratory domains. Citation analysis demonstrated that a small number of high-impact clinical trials accounted for the majority of citations, whereas many recent publications had not yet accumulated citations, reflecting the emerging nature of the field.

Conclusion: This study maps global research on tirzepatide in OSA, demonstrating

increasing integration of cardiometabolic and respiratory research and providing a framework for future clinical research and interdisciplinary collaboration.

Keywords: Tirzepatide, Obstructive Sleep Apnea, Bibliometrics, Scientific Mapping, Incretin-Based Therapies.

INTRODUCTION

Obstructive sleep apnea (OSA) is a prevalent yet frequently underdiagnosed sleep-related breathing disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of upper airway collapse during sleep, leading to intermittent hypoxia, sleep fragmentation, and excessive daytime sleepiness (1). OSA represents a major public health concern due to its well-established associations with cardiovascular disease, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and increased all-cause mortality (2,3). The global burden of OSA continues to rise in parallel with the increasing prevalence of obesity and metabolic syndrome, underscoring the complex and bidirectional relationship between sleep-disordered breathing and metabolic dysfunction (3,4).

Obesity represents one of the most important modifiable risk factors for OSA, contributing to upper airway narrowing, impaired neuromuscular control, and altered respiratory mechanics (5). Conversely, OSA exacerbates metabolic dysregulation through mechanisms such as chronic intermittent hypoxia, sympathetic nervous system activation, systemic inflammation, and hormonal imbalance, thereby worsening insulin resistance and cardiometabolic risk profiles (3).

Tirzepatide is a novel dual agonist of the glucose-dependent insulinotropic polypeptide (GIP) and glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptors that has demonstrated substantial efficacy in glycemic control and body weight reduction among patients with T2DM and obesity (6, 7). The clinical development and regulatory trajectory of tirzepatide has progressed rapidly, with initial approval for T2DM in 2022 followed by approval for chronic weight management in individuals with obesity in 2023, reflecting its expanding role in metabolic disease management. Large randomized controlled trials have shown that tirzepatide achieves superior metabolic outcomes compared with existing GLP-1

receptor agonists, including pronounced weight loss and improvements in glycemic parameters (6,7). Given the pivotal role of excess adiposity in the pathogenesis of OSA, these metabolic effects provide a strong biological rationale for exploring tirzepatide as a potential therapeutic option in patients with OSA.

Emerging clinical evidence suggests that incretin-based therapies may improve OSA severity primarily through weight reduction and metabolic modulation rather than direct airway effects (8). Recent large-scale clinical trials have further reinforced this hypothesis, with tirzepatide demonstrating significant improvements in OSA-related outcomes among individuals with obesity, positioning it as a promising pharmacologic intervention at the interface of metabolic and sleep medicine (9). Despite growing clinical and scientific interest, however, the literature addressing tirzepatide and OSA remains relatively limited, heterogeneous, and rapidly evolving.

Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative methodological approach that enables systematic evaluation of scientific output, research impact, and thematic evolution within a specific field by analyzing publication trends, citation patterns, collaborative networks, and keyword structures (10, 11). Although previous bibliometric studies have successfully characterized global research trends in OSA, to the best of our knowledge, there is currently no comprehensive bibliometric study specifically focusing on the emerging interface between incretin-based therapies and OSA. Against this background, the present study aimed to conduct a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of the global scientific literature on tirzepatide and OSA.

METHOD

Search Strategy

The Web of Science Core Collection (WoS; Clarivate Analytics, USA) database was systematically searched for publications published between 2022 and September 18, 2025, corresponding to the period following the initial clinical introduction of tirzepatide. As this study is based on bibliometric analysis of publicly available data, ethical approval was not required. The WoS database was selected as the primary data source because of its comprehensive bibliometric indicators,

standardized indexing structure, and widespread use in bibliometric research, which collectively make it particularly suitable for mapping scientific trends, citation patterns, and collaborative networks across different research domains (12).

The search timeframe was defined from 2022 onward, corresponding to the initial regulatory approval of tirzepatide for T2DM, reflecting the emergence of the drug as a clinically relevant therapeutic agent and its subsequent investigation in relation to OSA.

Strategy and MeSH Terms

The central hypothesis of this research is to identify the number, citation trends, and focal points of the most frequently cited international publications related to tirzepatide and OSA. To this end, appropriate access terms were compiled and combined, and relevant publications were searched using the WoS database. The search terms included 'tirzepatide and OSA', 'Obstructive Sleep Apnea', 'OSA', 'tirzepatide', 'Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome and tirzepatide', and 'OSA and tirzepatide'.

Data Collection and Analysis

The keywords used during the search covered all languages. The database search period for the published articles was defined as between 2022 and 2025. All document types indexed in the WoS database were included in the analysis to ensure a comprehensive representation of the available scientific output, given the emerging nature of research on tirzepatide in OSA and the limited number of publications. A total of 39 publications were included in the final analysis.

Bibliometric analysis is a quantitative methodological approach used to evaluate scientific output, citation patterns, and conceptual structures within a research field. It enables systematic assessment of research productivity, collaboration networks, and thematic evolution through performance analysis and science mapping techniques (10–14).

To obtain insights into the relevant scientific field, performance analysis, collaboration analysis, and scientific mapping were conducted based on authors, citation frequency,

co-authorship patterns, and keyword co-occurrence.

Performance Analysis

Publications were evaluated in terms of the most productive authors, countries, and institutions, as well as the most frequently cited journals and articles. Citation metrics and keyword co-occurrence patterns were also analyzed to assess research impact and productivity.

Collaboration Analysis

Scientific collaboration was assessed through co-authorship analysis among authors, institutions, and countries. Networks were constructed in which nodes represented entities and links indicated collaborative relationships.

Conceptual Structure Analysis (Multiple Correspondence Analysis)

Conceptual structure was examined using Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) based on author keywords. This approach identified patterns of association and thematic clustering according to keyword co-occurrence. The resulting two-dimensional map visualized major research themes and their relationships. The analysis was performed using the Bibliometrix package in R.

RESULTS

Publication Output and Citation Trends

A total of 39 publications related to tirzepatide and OSA were identified during the study period. The annual number of publications demonstrated a marked increase, particularly after 2023. One publication (2.56%) was recorded in 2022, followed by two publications (5.12%) in 2023. The number increased to 13 publications (33.33%) in 2024 and reached 23 publications (58.97%) in 2025 (Figure 1).

Citation analysis showed a similar temporal pattern. Publications from 2024 received the highest number of citations. Overall, the 39 publications accumulated a total of 363 citations, with a mean citation rate of 9.3 citations per article. Annual publication output and citation trends are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Annual publication output and citation trends for studies on tirzepatide and OSA. (Bars represent the number of publications per year, and the line represents the total number of citations.)

Geographic Distribution of Publications

Country Contributions

Country-based analysis showed that the United States contributed the highest number of publications, accounting for 22 records. Australia ranked second with 8 publications, followed by Germany with 4 publications. India and the United Kingdom each contributed 3 publications, while China and Italy accounted for 2 publications each. Country affiliation data were not available for 5 publications, which were therefore excluded from the country-level analysis. The distribution of publications by country is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of Publications by Country

Country	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
United States	22	56.41
Australia	8	20.51
Germany	4	10.25
India	3	7.69
United Kingdom	3	7.69
China	2	5.12
France	2	5.12
Greece	2	5.12
Italy	2	5.12
Poland	2	5.12
Belgium	1	2.56
Brazil	1	2.56
Egypt	1	2.56
Finland	1	2.56
Hungary	1	2.56
Ireland	1	2.56
Jordan	1	2.56
Netherlands	1	2.56
Portugal	1	2.56
Romania	1	2.56
Slovenia	1	2.56
Spain	1	2.56
Taiwan	1	2.56
Ukraine	1	2.56
Wales	1	2.56

*Percentages may exceed 100% due to multi-country collaborations.

International Collaboration Analysis

International collaboration was evaluated based on co-authorship among countries. The collaboration network demonstrated multiple inter-country connections, with collaborations observed primarily among North America, Europe, and Australia. The international collaboration network is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. International collaboration network between countries contributing to tirzepatide and OSA research. (Nodes represent countries, and links indicate co-authorship collaborations; node size is proportional to the number of publications.)

Keyword Frequency Analysis

Keyword frequency analysis indicated that “tirzepatide” was the most frequently occurring keyword (n = 31, 16.32%), followed by “obstructive sleep apnea” (n = 28, 14.74%), “obesity” (n = 25, 13.16%), “GLP-1 receptor agonist” (n = 21, 11.05%), and “OSA” (n = 19, 10.00%).

Other commonly occurring keywords included “sleep-disordered breathing” (n = 17, 8.95%), “type 2 diabetes” (n = 15, 7.89%), “GLP-1RAs” (n = 13, 6.84%), “SURMOUNT” (n = 11, 5.79%), and “cardiovascular outcomes” (n = 10, 5.26%). The word cloud visualization is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Word cloud visualization of keyword frequency. (Word size reflects relative frequency, with larger words indicating more frequent occurrence.)

Conceptual Structure Analysis

Conceptual structure mapping based on Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) identified three distinct thematic clusters. Cluster 1 included pharmacological and therapeutic terms such as tirzepatide, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and weight loss. Cluster 2 comprised cardiometabolic terms including obesity, insulin resistance, and metabolic syndrome. Cluster 3 included respiratory-related terms such as OSA and sleep-disordered breathing. The conceptual structure map based on keyword co-occurrence is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Conceptual structure map of tirzepatide and OSA research based on Multiple Correspondence Analysis. (Each point represents a keyword, and the distance between points reflects the degree of association.)

Journal and Citation Analysis

Among the 39 publications analyzed, a total of 363 citations were recorded. The most-cited article, published in the New England Journal of Medicine, received 268 citations. Other highly cited articles were published in Contemporary Clinical Trials, Biomedicines, Sleep, and Current Obesity Reports. Details of the cited publications are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Top Cited Publications on Tirzepatide and OSA

Rank	Title	First Author	Senior Author(s)	Journal	Total Citations	Average per Year
1	Tirzepatide for the Treatment of Obstructive Sleep Apnea and Obesity	Malhotra A	Grunstein RR et al.	New England Journal of Medicine	268	134
2	Tirzepatide for the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea: Rationale, design, and baseline characteristics of the SURMOUNT-OSA phase 3 trial	Malhotra A	Bednarik J et al.	Contemporary Clinical Trials	34	17
3	Integrated Management of Cardiovascular-Renal-Hepatic-Metabolic Syndrome: Expanding Roles of SGLT2is, GLP-1RAs, and GIP/GLP-1RAs	Theodorakis N	Nikolaou M	Biomedicines	17	17
4	Glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists for the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea: a meta-analysis	Li M	Lin H et al.	Sleep	10	5

5	Estimating Cardiovascular Benefits of Tirzepatide in Sleep Apnea and Obesity: Insight from the SURMOUNT-OSA Trials	Beccuti G	Broglio F et al.	Current Obesity Reports	7	3.5
6	Current perspectives on the use of GLP-1 receptor agonists in obesity-related obstructive sleep apnea: a narrative review	El-Solh AA	Gould E et al.	Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy	6	3
7	The pleiotropic effects of GLP-1 receptor agonists in patients with metabolic dysfunction-associated steatohepatitis	Alkhoury N	Charlton M et al.	Expert Opinion on Investigational Drugs	4	4
8	Metabolic bariatric surgery in face of new anti-obesity medications—10+1 challenges	Pantelis AG	Lapatsanis DP	Metabolism and Target Organ Damage	4	1.33
9	Tirzepatide for overweight and obesity management	Hamza M	Davies MJ et al.	Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy	3	1.5
10	CVOT summit report 2024: new cardiovascular, kidney, and metabolic outcomes	Schnell O	Almandoz J et al.	Cardiovascular Diabetology	2	2
11	What will the impact be of use of tirzepatide in patients with OSA?	Pack A	Grunstein RR et al.	Sleep	2	2
12	GLP-1 receptor agonists for the treatment of obstructive sleep apnea and obesity	Romariz L	Araujo B et al.	European Journal of Internal Medicine	2	2
13	Safety and efficacy of GLP-1 receptor agonists in patients with OSA: a systematic review and meta-analysis	Altobaishat O	Gadelmawla AF et al.	European Clinical Respiratory Journal	1	1
14	Tirzepatide for the Treatment of OSA and Obesity (corrigendum)	Malhotra A	—	New England Journal of Medicine	1	0.5
15	In adults with moderate-to-severe OSA and obesity, tirzepatide reduced apnea-hypopnea events vs placebo	Cheskin LJ	Rajagopal S	Annals of Internal Medicine	1	0.5
16	Effect of tirzepatide on weight loss in patients with OSA and obesity from SURMOUNT-1	Grunstein RR	Taylor R et al.	Sleep	1	0.5

*Only the first and senior authors are presented; full author lists are available in the original publications.

Journals, Document Types, and Languages

The 39 publications were distributed across 24 different journals. Sleep and Breathing accounted for 4 publications (10.26%),

followed by Expert Opinion on Pharmacotherapy and Sleep, each with 3 publications (7.69%). In terms of citation impact, the New England Journal of Medicine accounted for 268 citations.

Original research articles constituted the largest document category (n = 23), followed by abstracts (n = 13), meeting publications (n = 10), and review articles (n = 9). The distribution of document types is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Distribution of Document Types Among Included Publications

Document Types	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Original Articles	23	58.97
Abstract	13	33.33
Meeting	10	25.64
Review Article	9	23.07
Editorial Material	5	12.82
Other	5	12.82
Correction	4	10.25
Early Access	2	5.12
Clinical Trial	2	5.12
Letter	1	2.56

*Categories are not mutually exclusive; therefore, totals may exceed the number of publications.

Regarding language, 38 publications were published in English (97.44%), and one publication was published in German (2.56%).

Author Productivity, Institutional Contributions, and Collaboration Networks

A total of 98 authors contributed to the 39 publications included in the analysis. Josef

Bednarik was the most prolific author, appearing in 20 publications (51.28%), followed by Cathy Xie with 13 publications (33.33%) and Beverly Falcon with 12 publications (30.77%). The majority of authors (n = 80) contributed to only one publication.

Institutional analysis identified a total of 164 distinct affiliations. The most frequently represented institutions were the University of Illinois, Woolcock Institute of Medical Research, and the University of Sydney, each contributing to 7 publications (17.95%). Other major contributing institutions included the University of California System and Macquarie University, each with 5 publications (12.82%). Additional institutions such as Harvard University, Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin, and Eli Lilly appeared in 4 publications each (10.26%). The majority of institutions (n = 101, 61.59%) were represented by a single publication, and complete affiliation data were unavailable for 5 publications (12.82%).

Collaboration network analyses were conducted at the author, country, and institution levels based on co-authorship patterns, with total link strength used to quantify collaboration intensity. Author-, country-, and institution-level networks are presented in Figure 5A–C, respectively.

Figure 5 A

Figure 5 B

Figure 5 C

Figure 5. Collaboration networks based on co-authorship patterns and total link strength at the author (A), country (B), and institution (C) levels. (Nodes represent entities, and links indicate collaborative relationships; link thickness reflects collaboration strength.)

Citation Distribution

Across the 39 publications analyzed, a total of 363 citations were recorded. The five most-cited articles accounted for 336 citations (92.56%) of all citations. The most-cited article received 268 citations (73.83%), followed by articles with 34 (9.37%), 17 (4.68%), 10

(2.75%), and 7 (1.93%) citations, respectively. Citation analysis by publication year indicated that 2024 was the most-cited year. A substantial proportion of citations originated from publications in 2024, reflecting the recent emergence of high-impact studies in this field.

At the author level, Josef Bednarik appeared in 20 publications and accumulated a total of 258 citations. Institution-based citation analysis showed that the University of Pennsylvania contributed to 9 publications, receiving 204 total citations.

Regarding journal impact, the New England Journal of Medicine was the most cited journal with 268 citations (73.83%), followed by Contemporary Clinical Trials with 34 citations (9.37%) and Biomedicines with 17 citations (4.68%).

Publications classified as clinical trials (n = 2, 5.13%) accounted for 90 citations (24.79%), whereas review articles (n = 9, 23.08%) contributed 36 citations (9.92%).

Overall, 16 publications (41.03%) received at least one citation, whereas 23 publications

Table 4. Distribution of Publications by Research Area

Research Area	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Pharmacology & Pharmacy	25	64.10
Neurosciences & Neurology	24	61.54
Endocrinology & Metabolism	23	58.97
Nutrition & Dietetics	22	56.41
Respiratory System	16	41.03
Otorhinolaryngology	15	38.46
Research & Experimental Medicine	9	23.08
Cardiology	8	20.51
Medicine General & Internal	8	20.51
Clinical Neurology	6	15.38
Biochemistry & Molecular Biology	5	12.82
Gastroenterology & Hepatology	5	12.82
Surgery	5	12.82
Oncology	4	10.26
Radiology Nuclear Medicine Medical Imaging	4	10.26
Health Care Sciences & Services	3	7.69
Behavioral Sciences	2	5.13
Immunology	2	5.13
Physiology	2	5.13
Toxicology	7	17.95
Critical Care Medicine	1	2.56
Mathematics	1	2.56
Medical Laboratory Technology	1	2.56
Pathology	1	2.56
Urology & Nephrology	1	2.56

*Categories are not mutually exclusive; therefore, totals may exceed the number of publications.

DISCUSSION

The progressive increase in publications on tirzepatide and OSA, particularly after 2023, reflects a growing clinical interest in the metabolic dimensions of sleep-disordered breathing. This rise temporally coincides with the publication of large randomized controlled trials demonstrating the robust weight-loss and cardiometabolic effects of tirzepatide in patients

(58.97%) had not received citations at the time of analysis.

Web of Science Research Categories

Analysis of Web of Science subject categories revealed that the most frequently represented research areas among the 39 publications were Pharmacology & Pharmacy (n = 25), Neurosciences & Neurology (n = 24), and Endocrinology & Metabolism (n = 23). Other prominent categories included Nutrition & Dietetics (n = 22), Respiratory System (n = 16), and Otorhinolaryngology (n = 15). Additional categories were represented at lower frequencies, and the full distribution is presented in Table 4. As publications may be indexed under multiple Web of Science subject categories, percentages are not mutually exclusive and may exceed 100%.

with obesity and T2DM (6,7). Given the well-established dose-response relationship between body weight and OSA severity, these findings have likely accelerated research interest in incretin-based therapies for OSA. The parallel increase in citation activity suggests that early publications rapidly shaped scholarly attention, a pattern commonly observed in emerging research fields following landmark clinical studies (13).

The predominance of publications originating from the United States and Australia highlights the leading role of these regions in research at the intersection of metabolic disease and sleep medicine. This pattern is consistent with global bibliometric evidence indicating that countries with strong research infrastructure and international collaboration networks contribute disproportionately to high-impact scientific output (11, 13). Both countries benefit from well-developed academic–industry collaborations and early access to novel incretin-based therapies, facilitating the rapid translation of metabolic interventions into sleep-related research.

From a clinical perspective, the underrepresentation of low- and middle-income countries raises concerns regarding the global generalizability of current findings. Variations in obesity prevalence, OSA phenotypes, and healthcare access may influence disease presentation and treatment response, underscoring the need for broader geographic inclusion in future studies (4).

The international collaboration patterns identified in this analysis reflect the increasingly multinational nature of contemporary OSA and obesity research. Previous studies have demonstrated that international collaboration enhances research quality, citation impact, and methodological robustness, particularly in complex clinical fields requiring large and heterogeneous populations (13). Such collaboration is especially critical for pharmacologic trials, which require standardized outcome measures and diverse patient cohorts to ensure external validity.

Keyword analysis revealed a strong emphasis on tirzepatide, obesity, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and OSA, highlighting the current focus on metabolic mechanisms underlying sleep-disordered breathing. Accumulating evidence supports a close link between OSA, insulin resistance, visceral adiposity, and systemic inflammation, particularly in obesity-related phenotypes (2,5). Interventional studies have further demonstrated that incretin-based therapies, such as GLP-1 receptor agonists, may improve OSA severity primarily through weight reduction and metabolic modulation (8).

These findings support the potential role of metabolically targeted therapies as adjunctive strategies rather than replacements for established treatments such as continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP). Furthermore, the inclusion of all document types reflects the early-stage and rapidly evolving nature of this research field, where evidence is still emerging and not yet fully consolidated within peer-reviewed literature.

The identification of three main thematic clusters—pharmacological, cardiometabolic, and respiratory—illustrates the evolving conceptual framework of tirzepatide and OSA research. The close alignment between pharmacological and cardiometabolic themes reflects increasing interest in disease-modifying therapies targeting shared metabolic pathways. This conceptual convergence is consistent with phenotype- and endotype-based models of OSA, which emphasize individualized and mechanism-driven treatment approaches rather than uniform therapeutic strategies (15, 16).

The concentration of citations within a small number of high-impact publications, particularly those published in journals such as the *New England Journal of Medicine*, underscores the central role of landmark clinical trials in shaping research priorities. In clinical medicine, randomized controlled trials remain the highest level of evidence for therapeutic interventions and are therefore more likely to attract citations and influence clinical practice (17).

Consistent with this observation, original research articles demonstrated greater citation impact than review articles, which aligns with previous bibliometric findings indicating that primary data-driven studies tend to generate higher scientific impact in rapidly evolving research fields. The peak in citation activity observed in 2024 coincides with the publication of high-impact clinical evidence, suggesting a rapid and focused response of the research community to robust, outcome-driven data. Conversely, the observation that more than half of the publications have not yet accumulated citations likely reflects the recency of the literature and the well-recognized time lag between publication and citation uptake in rapidly evolving clinical research fields (12).

The predominance of English-language publications and their concentration in specialized sleep and metabolic journals are consistent with contemporary trends in biomedical publishing. This distribution further reflects the centralization of high-impact clinical research within internationally visible journals and underscores the importance of methodological rigor and clinical relevance for broader dissemination.

Finally, the clustering of scientific output among a limited number of authors and institutions suggests that research on tirzepatide and OSA remains in an early developmental phase, largely driven by centers with strong clinical trial capacity and industry partnerships (11). While such concentration may accelerate early discovery, broader institutional participation will be essential to enhance external validity and ensure equitable translation of research findings into routine clinical practice.

The dominance of pharmacology, endocrinology, and neuroscience-related categories highlights the multidisciplinary nature of tirzepatide and OSA research. The concurrent representation of respiratory and otorhinolaryngology disciplines reflects the complex metabolic, neurological, and airway-related phenotype of OSA (1).

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the analysis was limited to the Web of Science database; therefore, relevant publications indexed exclusively in other databases such as Scopus or PubMed may have been missed. Second, citation counts are dynamic and may change over time; thus, the findings reflect the literature at the time of data retrieval. Third, all document types indexed in the database were included without restriction, which may have introduced heterogeneity due to the inclusion of abstracts, meeting materials, and non-peer-reviewed content. However, this approach was deliberately adopted given the limited and emerging nature of the literature on tirzepatide in OSA, in order to provide a more comprehensive and inclusive overview of the available evidence. Finally, as a bibliometric study, this analysis characterizes research patterns and trends but does not evaluate the

clinical efficacy or therapeutic outcomes of tirzepatide in patients with OSA.

CONCLUSION

This bibliometric analysis outlines the emerging scientific landscape at the intersection of tirzepatide and OSA. The rapid growth in publications and citations reflects increasing interest in metabolic-based strategies for OSA, particularly in obesity-related phenotypes. Current research is largely shaped by high-impact clinical trials and concentrated within a limited number of countries and institutions, highlighting both the influence of landmark studies and existing geographic disparities. Thematic mapping demonstrates a gradual integration of cardiometabolic and sleep medicine perspectives. Although the literature remains relatively recent and heterogeneous, this study provides a structured overview of research productivity, collaboration patterns, and conceptual trends, offering a foundation for future hypothesis-driven clinical research and interdisciplinary collaboration.

DESCRIPTIONS

No financial support.

No conflict of interest.

Ethics approval and consent to participate: This study is based on a bibliometric analysis of publicly available data obtained from the Web of Science database and does not involve human participants or animal subjects. Therefore, ethical committee approval was not required in accordance with international research guidelines and the journal's ethical policies.

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